

Characterization of Fatigue Delamination Growth in a Circular Notched CFRP
by Scanning Acoustic Microscope and Influences of Water Absorption

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the influences of circular hole and water absorption on the fatigue delamination growth behavior of a carbon fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite. The composites used were quasi-isotropic and cross-ply laminates. Fatigue delamination was non-destructively and quantitatively examined with a scanning acoustic microscope (SAM), operating in the reflection mode. The usefulness and good ability of nondestructive delamination evaluation by the SAM was demonstrated. The influences of stacking sequence and circular notch as well as water absorption on the initiation and growth behavior of delamination were discussed.

Key Words: CFRP, epoxy matrix, fatigue, delamination, circular hole, nondestructive inspection, scanning acoustic microscopy

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites incorporating long fibers and matrices whose mechanical properties are very different are typical anisotropic materials. The fracture mechanism, in particular, in laminated composites that are used for structural components is thus extremely complicated when compared with that of conventional isotropic metallic materials [1]; fracture processes include matrix cracking, fiber breakage, fiber/matrix interfacial debonding, and delamination. Water absorption also severely affected not only static strength but also fatigue strength [2]. For such composite component having notches including a circular hole, the fracture processes may be more complicated. Consequently, the application of these anisotropic composite materials with notches to machinery components and structures requires precise clarification of the damage development.

Various techniques have been used in composite materials to detect the initiation and growth of internal damage [3]; the X-ray radiographic technique, the replicate technique and optical microscope or SEM (scanning electron microscope) methods, and the de-ply technique. However, these traditional methods are destructive or they give only through-the-thickness information on damage or the location in a two-dimensional manner. In contrast with these, the recently developed scanning acoustic microscope (SAM) technique [2] is very helpful for observing the initiation and propagation of internal damage in composites; it is a non-destructive technique and gives not only through-the-thickness information, but also interply information on the onset and growth of damage, in particular, delamination, enabling the location of delamination to be determined.

The present paper describes the influences of circular hole and water absorption on the development of fatigue damage of quasi-isotropic and cross-ply laminated carbon fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite, with special emphasis on non-destructive observations of the initiation and propagation of internal damage of delamination by scanning acoustic microscopy.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material tested was a middle-temperature cured carbon fiber reinforced epoxy matrix laminated composite material with two types of stacking sequence: $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$ quasi-isotropic laminates and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{4S}$ cross-ply laminates. Fibers were Pyrofil T-1 by Mitsubishi Rayon Corp., Japan (tensile strength: 3.53 GPa, elastic modulus: 235 GPa), and the matrix was 828 epoxy resin. The curing condition was $90^\circ\text{C} \times 60$ minutes followed by $130^\circ\text{C} \times 60$ minutes. Fiber volume fraction and average thickness for both laminates were about 60% and 2.3mm. Circular notched specimens with 40 mm in width and 200 mm in length were used. A 8-mm circular hole was drilled in the center of each specimen. Smooth rectangular specimens with 190 mm in length and 10 mm in width were also used.

Fatigue tests were performed with a electro-hydraulic servo-controlled fatigue testing machine, with a sinusoidal wave form at a stress ratio of 0.1 and stress cycle frequency of 1 Hz. Tests were done on both dry and wet specimens, which were respectively preconditioned in air at room temperature, and in deionized water at 80°C for about two months. Water gain ranged from 2.13% to 2.52%. For dry specimens, tests were conducted in laboratory air, whereas for wet specimens in deionized water at 25°C . Compliance changes during fatigue tests, which are considered to express the degree of macroscopic damage states of a specimen, were measured with a personal computer (HP9000, Model 310, Hewlett Packard Corp.). Compliance values adopted were averages of succeeding 40 cycles. The elongation of a specimen was measured with a clip-on gage (gage length: 40 mm).

We closely examined the initiation and propagation of internal damage with a scanning acoustic microscope (UH-3: Olympus Optic Corp., Japan). We selected a 50 MHz ultrasonic pulse wave, and set a gate time of 50 ns to observe interply damage and 1400 ns to observe through-the-thickness information in a laminate. The SAM image was directly transferred to a personal computer (HP Vectra ES, Hewlett Packard Corp.), and the delaminated areas were extracted by binary treatments to obtain changes in the delaminated area during a test. In calculating, delamination within the gage length was concerned. In the case of circular notched specimens, delamination around the hole was calculated. Changes in delaminated area were expressed by normalization of the delaminated area divided by "the area of specimen", which was defined by specimen width multiplied by gage length (40 mm). In the case of a circular notched specimen, "the area of specimen" excluded the area of the hole.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Delamination Growth Behavior

In the case of smooth specimens, edge delamination was initiated and propagated in quasi-isotropic laminates, although no edge delamination was detected in cross-ply laminates. As for circular notched specimens, delamination was initiated and propagated around a circular notch for both laminates. The delamination behavior in each specimen is summarized as follows:

3.1.1 Quasi-isotropic Laminates

Figure 1 shows the SAM photographs showing the delamination behavior of a smooth specimen. In both dry and wet specimens, edge delamination between the 1st/2nd interply was not observed, although delamination at the 2nd/3rd, 3rd/4th and 4th/5th (figure omitted) interplies was clearly observed. There was no difference of the location and shape of delamination between the dry and wet

Figure 1. SAM Photographs of quasi-isotropic smooth laminate (dry specimen, maximum stress: 422 MPa, $n = 6 \times 10^4$ cycles)

specimens. However, delamination in wet specimens grew faster than dry specimens, indicating the degradation of interfacial and interlaminar strength owing to water absorption. Delamination at the 3rd/4th interply grew faster than that at the 4th/5th interply, because matrix transverse cracking in the 90° plies promoted the adjacent interlaminar delamination.

In the case of circular-notched specimens, longitudinal matrix cracks first initiated at the edges of the hole and the associated delamination at the 1st/2nd and 2nd/3rd interplies grew: see Figure 2. We have to note that the delamination

Figure 2. SAM Photographs of quasi-isotropic circular notched laminate (dry specimens, maximum stress: 329 MPa, $n = 8 \times 10^4$ cycles)

Figure 3. SAM Photographs of cross-ply circular notched laminate (dry specimen, maximum stress: 427 MPa, $n = 4.5 \times 10^4$ cycles)

at the 1st/2nd interply occurred because of stress concentration by a circular hole, which was not observed in smooth specimens. The difference of delamination behavior between the dry and wet specimens was not observed, similarly to smooth specimens. Delamination at the 2nd/3rd interply propagated in a manner that the shape of delamination became symmetric. However, the delamination at the 1st/2nd interply preferentially grew greater in the -45 degree-direction. In this laminates, the fibers in the +45 degree ply run through the specimen width unlike the fibers in the -45 degree ply, and therefore, the bearing stress in the -45 degree-fibers became high, leading to high interlaminar stress.

3.1.2 Cross-ply Laminates

Unlike the quasi-isotropic laminates, edge delamination of smooth specimens was not observed. SAM inspection showed that the string-shaped, transverse bright zones increased with stress cycles. These transverse bright zones were caused by transverse matrix cracks or transverse interfacial debonding, indicating that transverse intralaminar damage was dominant in smooth cross-ply laminates. SAM inspection was also able to visualize transverse damage, which was traditionally inspected with such X-ray radiographic techniques. Another interesting point observed in wet smooth specimens was that blister at the 1st/2nd interply grew, which had been formed during preconditioning in hot water.

Figure 3 shows the SAM photographs of a circular notched dry specimens. In both dry and wet specimens, longitudinal matrix cracks first initiated at the edges of the hole, and thereby growing greater the associated delamination at the 1st/2nd and 2nd/3rd interplies in the longitudinal direction. In the case of wet specimens, more slender delamination than the case of dry specimens grew as well as blister growth, similarly to the cases of wet smooth specimens.

3.2 Relation between Compliance and Delaminated Area

Changes in compliance of each specimen and delaminated areas with the progress of stress cycles were measured. Compliance adopted here was a normalized value, which was defined by compliance divided by the initial compliance at the beginning of a test, which will be simply referred to 'compliance'. Changes in compliance and delaminated area were basically similar, irrespective of specimen type and preconditioning condition: both compliance and delaminated area of wet specimens were larger than those of dry specimens, with higher growth rate, resulting from degradation of matrix material and interfacial and interlaminar strength.

(a) Through-the-thickness delaminated area
 Figure 4. Relationship between delaminated area and compliance of quasi-isotropic smooth laminates.

In order to clarify a dominating factor on compliance changes, the relation between compliance and delaminated area was obtained. Figure 4(a) shows the relationship between "through-the-thickness delaminated area" (which was obtained from the SAM images of through-the-thickness information on delamination) and compliance of both dry and wet quasi-isotropic smooth specimens. Figures 4(b) and (c) respectively show the relationship between compliance and each delaminated area at the 2nd/3rd and 3rd/4th interplies. These figures show that changes in compliance are dependent neither on the through-the-thickness delaminated area nor on that at the 3rd/4th interply, rather on that at the 2nd/3rd interply. This is because the delamination at the 3rd/4th interply situated just under the delamination at the 2nd/3rd interply, and thus the delaminated area at the 2nd/3rd interply almost equaled the area of the third ply (-45 degree-ply), which bore no loading. In other words, compliance changes of the quasi-isotropic smooth specimens were determined by the area of no-load-bearing -45 degree ply.

(b) Delaminated area at the 2nd/3rd interply

(c) Delaminated area at the 3rd/4th interply

Figure 4. Relationship between delaminated area and compliance of quasi-isotropic smooth laminates.

In the case of circular notched quasi-isotropic specimens, compliance changes were not dependent on through-the-thickness delamination area (figure is omitted), but on the delaminated area at the 1st/2nd interply (Figure 5). In this case, the delamination at the 1st/2nd interply associated with longitudinal matrix crack occurred at the both sides of a hole, and the zero-degree ply bore no load.

Figure 6 shows the relationship between compliance and through-the-thickness delaminated area of the circular notched cross-ply specimens. In this laminates, the delaminated area at the 1st/2nd interply almost equaled the through-the-thickness delaminated area. As for each dry and wet specimen, there was respectively good linear relationship between the compliance and the delaminated area, although the slopes of dry and wet specimens differed. In the binarization treatments, the calculated areas were restricted to the area around the hole: delaminated areas which were plotted in the figure involved only those initiating from the hole and the blister growth in wet specimens was excluded. There-

Figure 5. Relationship between delaminated area at the 1st/2nd interply and compliance of quasi-isotropic circular notched laminates.

Figure 6. Relationship between delaminated area at the through-the-thickness delaminated area compliance of cross-ply circular notched laminates.

fore, the compliance of wet specimens was larger than that of dry specimens in Figure 6. Considering these, the delaminated areas including blister growth in wet specimens were calculated and the result is shown by a broken line in the figure. Compared this broken line with the result of dry specimens, the difference of the slopes between the two became small. These indicate that the compliance of dry specimens was mainly dependent on the delamination at the 1st/2nd interply, whereas in the case of wet specimens compliance was dependent both on delamination and blister at the 1st/2nd interply.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The influences of circular notch and water absorption on fatigue delamination growth behavior of $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$ quasi-isotropic and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{4S}$ cross-ply laminated carbon fiber reinforced composites were investigated, with special emphasis on nondestructive inspection of the initiation and growth of delamination by scanning acoustic microscopy. These results yielded the following conclusions.

1. Scanning acoustic microscopy is very helpful for nondestructive ply-to-ply inspection of internal damage of delamination in laminated composites.
2. In the case of quasi-isotropic laminates, edge delamination of smooth specimens initiated and propagated mainly at the interplies at the 2nd/3rd, 3rd/4th, and 5th/6th plies, leading to no-load bearing plies of the third ply (-45 degree-ply). In the case of circular notched specimen, delamination at the 1st/2nd and 2nd/3rd interplies initiated at the edges of the hole, without edge delamination.
3. In the case of cross-ply laminates, no edge delamination occurred in smooth specimens. However, SAM inspection showed transverse matrix cracking in the 90 degree-ply. In wet specimens, additional blister growth at the 1st/2nd interply was observed. In the case of circular notched specimens, delamination at the 1st/2nd and the 2nd/3rd interplies initiated at edges of the hole.
4. Water absorption does not influence the basic delamination growth behavior, although the delamination growth rates of wet specimens were accelerated.
5. In the case of quasi-isotropic laminates, compliance of smooth specimens was determined by the delaminated area at the 2nd/3rd interply. However, delaminated area at the 1st/2nd interplies determined compliance of circular notched specimens. As for circular notched cross-ply specimens, there was good relationship between compliance and through-the-thickness delaminated area including blister growth in wet specimens.

References

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